

CONTAGIOUS VIRAL DISEASES OF BIRDS

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Among birds, as among all living things, there are various types of diseases, these are viral, bacterial, parasitic, fungal, caused by toxins and others. In my scientific article, I focused on viral diseases of birds. Viral diseases are contagious diseases among wild and domestic birds.

Marek's disease - Morbus Marek is a chronically occurring viral disease of poultry of the chicken order, characterized by neoplastic processes in parenchymal organs and inflammation of the peripheral nervous system.

Viral hepatitis of ducks - Hepatitis virosa anatum is a contagious viral disease mainly of ducklings up to 4 weeks of age, characterized by predominant liver damage.

Infectious laryngotracheitis of birds - Laryngotracheitis infectiosa avium, a contagious viral disease characterized by hemorrhagic inflammation of the pharynx and trachea.

Smallpox is a common viral disease of poultry. It is characterized by the development of isolated nodular, proliferative skin lesions on non-feathered parts of the body (skin form) or lesions on the mucous membrane of the upper respiratory tract, oral cavity and esophagus (diphtheria form).

Avian pasteurellosis (cholera) is an infectious disease of birds caused by pasteurels and manifested in acute course by symptoms of septicemia with the formation of multiple hemorrhages on serous and mucous membranes.

Pullorosis (typhus) of birds Pullorosis (Typus) avium, an infectious disease of chickens characterized by damage to the intestines, parenchymal organs in young animals and degeneration of ovarian follicles in adult birds.

Newcastle disease (Latin Pseudopestis avium), bird pseudocuma, or Asian bird plague is a viral disease of birds characterized by pneumonia, encephalitis and multiple spot hemorrhagic lesions of internal organs.

In my research papers, I have studied smallpox in turkeys. If smallpox has appeared in turkeys, then they are placed separately from healthy birds. Turkeys are the most sensitive domestic birds to the smallpox virus. They can get sick from a bird that has already picked up the disease. And for this, the turkey must be in contact with a sick pet. Also, the virus can enter the body through feed, water and much more. Insects that can bite a bird (bird louse) are

also carriers of infection.

Smallpox ulcers around the eyes and beak of a turkey

The disease was studied in turkeys for 2-3 months and in chickens for 3-4 months, smallpox in poultry or diphtheria is a contagious viral disease, observed mainly in poultry at the age of 4-12 months, which is manifested by the development of smallpox exanthema on the untrimmed areas of the scalp, legs, on the crest, earrings, lobes, around the beak and nasal openings, on the mandible and eyelids or diphteroid lesions of the mucous membranes of the oral cavity, upper respiratory tract and conjunctiva. We observed more in turkeys on the beak, around the eye, in the conjunctiva, on the shoulder joint, and also on the knee joint. Chickens infected from turkeys often had ulcers on the beak, around the beak, and conjunctiva.

Chickens were smeared with a 5% solution of iodine, fucortsin, lugol was sprayed into the beak, isolated from sick turkeys, also watered with baitril, this remedy was mixed into food.

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